

Sensitivity and Dynamic Range of a Wideband RF Analyzer Based on Parametric Multicasting

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Abstract—Sensitivity and dynamic range data is presented for a wideband staring RF spectrum analyzer based on parametric multicasting and spectral slicing with a periodic optical filter.

Keywords—microwave photonics; four-wave mixing; parametric processing

I. INTRODUCTION

Optical domain parametric mixing has been used to perform wavelength conversion and multicasting for digital data applications [1] and more recently designs for a RF spectrum analyzer / channelizer using multicasting have been proposed and demonstrated [2, 3]. Alternative photonic channelizer configurations have also been proposed [4]. A design and implementation of a wideband, staring (100% duty cycle) optical domain RF spectrum analyzer (SA) based on parametric multicasting covering an 18 GHz RF instantaneous bandwidth (IBW) with ~250 MHz resolution bandwidth (RBW) was previously presented [3]. In this paper, we report on sensitivity and single tone dynamic range (DR) measurements for a similar SA design employing modified signal path and parametric mixer design.

II. SYSTEM DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION

The SA design is shown in Fig. 1. Its operation can be broken down in three stages as follows. In the front end stage a single tone RF signal is imprinted onto an optical carrier at 1552.1nm using carrier-suppressed amplitude modulation. The signal is amplified and spectrally replicated to multiple copies via four-wave mixing (FWM) in a three-stage parametric mixer. The mixer stage consists of 110m of a highly nonlinear fiber (HNLF1) followed by a time domain compressor stage (20m SMF), and a second 200m-long dispersion-flattened HNLF stage (HNLF2). Two amplified laser diodes (P1, P2) with spacing $\Delta f_p = 199.5$ GHz serve as pumps for parametric mixing. The total optical pump power at the input to the parametric mixer is ~28 dBm.

The backend stage consists of a pump filter, and a periodic narrowband Fabry-Perot etalon filter (FP) that slices a narrow band equal to its passband width $\delta f = 250$ MHz out of each signal copy. The wavelengths of the pumps and a signal are tuned so that the signal comb spacing, Δf_s , differs from the free spectral range of the etalon (100GHz) by the passband width, $\Delta f_s = \Delta f_p / 2 = 100\text{GHz} - \delta f$, resulting in a Vernier relationship that provides spectral slicing of the copies. Spectral slices are routed to separate optical channels by a 100 GHz spaced arrayed waveguide grating (AWG) and the power in the channels is read out using a photodetector array.

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Fig. 1. Experimental setup: pumps (P1, P2), signal laser(S), HNLF- highly nonlinear fiber, SMF-single mode fiber

III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The front end / mixer configuration can generate more than 100 pump copies (Fig. 2) and 200 signal copies over 20THz-optical bandwidth. As an example, to analyze 18GHz instantaneous RF bandwidth with 250MHz resolution would require 72 signal copies that would cover 7.2THz optical bandwidth. As shown in Fig. 2, the mixer shows good performance across 7.2 THz bandwidth, with optical signal-to-noise ratio (OSNR) of the pump copies better than 143dBm/Hz and gain variation within 5dB.

To characterize performance of the SA we measured sensitivity and DR of 10-channels that select spectral copies between 9-13GHz.

Fig. 2. Output of HNLF monitored with OSA shows 20THz wide pump comb. Resolution limited by OSA 10 GHz RBW.

Fig. 3. RF input signal sensitivity for a range of signal path optical powers, P_s : 0dBm(\diamond), 3dBm(\square), 6dBm(Δ)

The RF input signal sensitivity is determined as a minimum detectable input RF power. It is characterized as a function of RF frequency with the optical power in the signal path (P_s) as a parameter (Fig. 3). For the highest P_s of 6dBm, minimum detectable RF power in 4 channels is better than -50dBm (250 MHz RBW) and for 8 channels better than -45dBm. The other two channels have signal copies with lower power and OSNR, and therefore poorer sensitivity. Larger P_s results in higher power of signal copies and consequently better sensitivity as shown.

However, higher P_s also results in larger spurious signals that are generated by higher-order four-wave mixing process. These spurious signals limit the dynamic range of the system. As an example, Fig. 4 shows reponse of the SA channels to RF signal swept from 2-20GHz. Each colored line corresponds to the output of a single channel. f_{ch} is the corresponding channel RF frequency and Δf_{pc} is the frequency difference between pump and carrier. Three distinct spurs are detectable in each channel: 1) $f_{ch}/3$ corresponding to FWM between two signal sidebands, 2) $f_{ch}/2$ corresponding to FWM between optical carrier and one of the signal sidebands, and 3) $(\Delta f_{pc}-f_{ch})/2$ corresponding to cascaded FWM of one of the signal sidebands with a pump and mixing of this product with the optical carrier.

Fig. 5 illustrates the measurements of dynamic range. Single tone dynamic range was determined by measuring the difference between the RF signal power at which all spurious

Fig. 4. Normalized channel output with frequency swept RF signal. Each color represents response of a single channel. Spurious peaks are marked.

Fig. 5. Dynamic range in 250 MHz bandwidth for a range of signal path optical powers: 0dBm(\diamond), 3dBm(\square), 6dBm(Δ)

signals decrease below the noise floor and the minimum detectable RF power. A general trend observed is that the dynamic range improves as P_s is decreased. This is expected because the spurious signals decrease faster than the sensitivity degrades as P_s is lowered.

The dynamic range for two channels is 41dB at signal path optical power of 0dBm, while for 7 out of ten channels it is better than 33dB. The channels with low dynamic range correspond to the channels with poor sensitivity as discussed in Fig.3.

IV. CONCLUSION

In order to achieve good RF SA sensitivity and dynamic range across the RF IBW, it is necessary to maintain good OSNR of the parametrically generated signal copies across the optical bandwidth of the comb. High sensitivity SA operation requires minimizing pump and signal carrier feed-through that is done in the current system by carrier-suppression and pump filtering. In addition to minimizing pump and signal feed-through, large dynamic range SA operation also requires minimizing spurious signals such as undesired higher-order parametric mixing terms. It has been demonstrated that SA sensitivity increases with increased optical power in the signal path, while the dynamic range decreases due to generation of higher-order mixing spurs. Further research will focus on implementing methods to mitigate the spurious signals and optimize signal copy OSNR through mixer and system design, as well as on further characterization of full system performance.

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